

Artificial Intelligence in Education: Applications and Tools for Supporting Educators and Students

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Abstract

In this talk, we will introduce education professionals to two innovative AI applications, "Teacher Mate" and "Study Buddy," developed under the AI4EDU project (<https://ai4edu.eu>). Funded by the EU, AI4EDU aims to create and evaluate next-generation intelligent educational assistants powered by advanced AI and language technologies. These tools are designed to support teaching and learning through engaging, flexible, and effective interactions while reducing the administrative burdens educators face in their daily activities.

Both applications leverage Large Language Models (LLMs) and techniques like Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) to provide practical, reliable, and context-specific support. "Teacher Mate" is an AI-powered assistant designed to optimize teachers' daily tasks, including lesson planning, formative assessment, and administrative documentation. It offers personalized suggestions, generates tailored teaching materials, and supports classroom management by automating routine processes. This allows educators to focus more on meaningful interactions with students, thereby enhancing the overall learning experience.

Similarly, "Study Buddy" acts as a personalized learning assistant for students, helping them study, complete assignments, and review concepts effectively. It offers customized educational content, interactive exercises, and revision support based on individual learning needs. By integrating national school textbooks from four European countries (Greece, Sweden, Ireland, and Cyprus) for both a science and a humanities subject, Study Buddy ensures that the generated materials are not only practical and reliable but also aligned with local curricula and educational standards.

Throughout our talk, we will explore the functionalities of both applications and demonstrate their potential for planning, developing, and implementing teaching, learning, and assessment activities. We will also share insights from pilot implementations across diverse educational settings in Europe, highlighting the real-world impact of these AI tools in supporting both educators and learners.

Key words: Artificial Intelligence, Education, Chatbots